

A March towards Dairy Revolution

Ruksana Majid*, Uzma Bashir¹ and Aasima Rafiq²

Corresponding author: *Assistant Professor, Division of AGB, FVSC & AH, SKUAST-Kashmir

1 SMS, Soil Science, KVK Srinagar, SKUAST-Kashmir

2 SMS, Food Science & Technology, KVK Srinagar, SKUAST-Kashmir

Livestock is emerging as an important sector in the economy of Jammu and Kashmir and plays an important role in the socio-economic development of Jammu and Kashmir. In Jammu and Kashmir about 80 percent of the population lives in the rural areas and about 60 per cent of the revenue is generated by the agriculture and animal husbandry sector. Dairying is climatically viable and has a potential source of additional income for the rural people of Jammu and Kashmir. With the emerging units, startups and government-sponsored schemes, the dairy sector in Jammu and Kashmir is thriving. Government with the help of farmers and dairy units is successful in producing 70 lakh litres of milk per day. Kashmir alone produces 40 lakh while Jammu produces 30 lakh liters, respectively. “White revolution is becoming popular and also marching on the path.

Situation analysis/problem statement

Small holder dairy production is increasingly becoming popular in whole of the Kashmir valley. However, feed and fodder shortage in winter is a major constraint to these dairy producers. The same problem was faced by Mr. Bilal Ahmad Lone, a resident of Noorbagh Qamarwari, Srinagar, who was running a dairy farm of 10 cows from last 20 years. He used to get a good profit in summer when there is plenty of green fodder available in his field but in winter he was facing a multitude of issues ranging from malnutrition, deteriorating health condition, reduction in milk production, loss of body weight, disease outbreaks and reproduction disorders. During the harsh winter, the major fodders available are paddy, wheat or maize straw, together with hay and concentrated feeds. One major and most common problem which every farmer is facing is the shortage of quality fodder in extreme weather conditions of winter. This feed and fodder shortage in winter is a major constraint to every dairy producer in valley. Most of these farmers are having very limited land resources. The production of green fodders throughout the year is also

impossible owing to the extreme cold climate. This shortage is the main hindrance in maintaining the health and production of livestock. To supply nutritious fodder in winter he was purchasing silage from outside state at very high rates and was incurring huge losses on feed bills.

Interventions by KVK, Srinagar

Green fodder supplement is essential to enhance rumen function for bovine animals. Conservation of excessive green fodder, available during its peak growing season in the form of silage could meet this necessary quality dietary requirement of dairy animals and would lessen the burden on small dairy farmers by avoiding buying of hay, concentrates and straw during harsh winter months. After evaluating mentioned problem, KVK Srinagar decided to address his issues by taking a multipronged approach. It was started by organizing awareness programs on silage making in that area. Many demonstrations on preparation of silage were also conducted. The farmer was also provided quality Maize fodder seed (KDFM1- A SKUAST-K Variety which is having a good biomass yield and ideal for silage making) under OFT Programme. He was also given a 7 days Skill Training on Dairy production. He was taken on an exposure visit to Mountain Livestock Research Institute Manasbal, SKUAST-K, Where he practically learnt how to make silage in bulk. An FLD on Urea Molasses Mineral Block (UMMB) was also laid in that area and the concerned farmer was a main beneficiary. He was also advised to prepare the concentrate feed for his livestock at his own farm and was provided formulation for economic ration preparation.

Output

- Farmer started to prepare silage of his own and in the first year he made 130 quintals of quality silage, and was totally independent on silage import and was able to save Rs.75000/year on feed bills in the winter.
- Farmer has now extended his farm from 10 cows to 15 cow unit.
- Farmer now preparing the concentrate feed himself, and is saving Rs. 54000/ year (Rs. 300/ quintal of feed).
- Farmer is now producing almost 150 kgs of milk per day and is earning Rs.70000/ month.

Impact

More dairy farmers from the village and adjacent villages have emulated this technology inspired by the beneficiary. The success has been achieved distinctively over the short period of time in a sustainable manner.

